

THE COST OF DATA CENTRES

Modelling the impact of data centres on electricity bills for Irish households

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Executive Summary

- This report finds that high data centre energy demand in Ireland, combined with dependence on gas-fired power in the Irish electricity market, is creating additional costs for Irish households.
- Given the extraordinary volatility of fossil fuel pricing in recent years, and likely in the future, **the dependency on gas in the power system combined with high and steadily increasing data centre energy demand makes Irish households further exposed to wholesale electricity cost increases.**
- The average household may have paid an estimated **€360** in additional electricity costs between 2015-2023 due to the intensity of data centre presence on the Irish Single Electricity Market (ISEM) grid putting upward pressure on prices. Cumulatively for all Irish households, this data centre price effect was as high as **€715 million**.
- Some **73%** of these past costs would have been incurred throughout 2021-2023 following the energy market crisis of that period. This is equivalent to an estimated **€263** paid by the average household in a three-year period.
- Depending on the growth of the data centre sector in the future, the average Irish household could expect to pay a further approximated **€295 (low demand scenario), €461 (median demand scenario), and €644 (high demand scenario) cumulatively** in the 10 year period 2025-2034. For all households combined, this scales to **€633 million, €991 million, and €1.43 billion** respectively for these demand scenarios.
- Scenarios also modelled the potential impact of a future price shock due to a hypothetical energy crisis, which could result in costs as high as **€726 million, €1.11 billion and €1.6 billion cumulatively between 2025-2034 across three electricity demand scenarios** for all households combined.
- When disaggregated by income quintile, estimates suggest that the cumulative total of data centre effects on households bills from 2015-2023 was **€286 for the lowest income group, and €428 for highest income households.**
- In 2022, a year of an energy crisis leading to extreme price spikes in wholesale electricity markets, the data centre cost effect was equivalent to an estimated **8.5% of total average residential bills.**
- Whilst more ambitious expansion of renewables capacity in the future can reduce the wholesale price effect of data centres, in the vast majority of scenarios modelled it is not sufficient to meaningfully displace the data centre-gas dependence cost effect associated with projected rises in data centre energy demand from 2025-2034, due to the projected scale of data centre demand.
- Policy decisions by the Irish government can significantly change the estimated data centre price effect. Scenarios modelled in this report show that placing limits on data centre energy demand and pursuing more ambitious renewables development, even in

the event of a price shock, could save Irish households an estimated **€435 cumulatively from 2025-2034.**

1. Introduction

In the last decade, data centres have become a significant feature of the multinational corporate economy in Ireland. Their extraordinary consumption of energy has accelerated in recent years to unprecedented levels in Ireland and around the world, presenting a significant opportunity cost to Irish society in the context of mounting climate, planetary and social crises.

Ireland has the highest share of data centre power consumption of any country in Europe (Cremona and Czyzak, 2025¹), and data centres consume more power than all urban households in the Irish state combined. From 2015 to the peak recorded quarterly usage in the third quarter of 2024, the share of total power consumed by data centres in Ireland rose from 4.4% to 23.9%, a more than four-fold increase (CSO, 2025)².

The Irish economy, like all global North economies, has transgressed fragile planetary limits, with energy and resource consumption, and associated waste (such as greenhouse gas emissions), far beyond sustainable limits (O’Neill et al, 2018; Fanning et al, 2025). Against this background, the rapid growth of data centres in Ireland and beyond presents a significant challenge to sustainability.

Proponents of data centre expansion promote their indirect economic benefits, particularly as a fiscal dependence on the corporate tax receipts of multinational tech giants has intensified in recent years (Cronin, 2026)³. Research has indicated, however, that the direct economic benefits of data centres relative to other sectors are remarkably low – from the perspective of labour intensity (jobs created and maintained per unit of output), industry claims about job creation are exaggerated, and pale in comparison to production in other sectors (Besliu et al, 2025)⁴. Taking into account the intense resource needs of data centres, this suggests that the socio-economic benefits as a ratio of resource use may be significantly lower than other sectors.

Other economic costs are clear, too. The sheer scale of resource and energy consumption can also inflate wholesale electricity prices (Saul et al, 2025⁶), create transmission-induced wholesale cost increases (Mamkhezri et al, 2025⁷), increase requirements for infrastructural maintenance and expansion, and can lead to disproportionate application of grid charges to households (CRU, 2025)⁸, and so on. In effect, these cost-shifting mechanisms socialise the costs of data centre expansion to households and small businesses, to facilitate further growth in some of the most profitable corporations on earth.

In Ireland, a significant literature gap exists which empirically assesses the direct, indirect and opportunity costs of a growing data centre sector. This report seeks to contribute to filling this

¹ <https://ember-energy.org/app/uploads/2025/06/Grids-for-data-centres-in-Europe.pdf>

² <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-dcmec/datacentresmeteredelectricityconsumption2024/keyfindings/>

³ <https://www.fiscalcouncil.ie/more-concentration-more-risk-three-firms-account-for-almost-half-of-irelands-corporation-tax-revenues/>

⁴ <https://algorithmwatch.org/en/infrastructure-intrusion-conflict-data-center/>

⁵ One analysis has found that one job was returned in Virginia (USA) through \$33 million in capital investment - <https://aprs.scot/resources/employment-and-data-centres-aprs-report/>

⁶ <https://www.bloomberg.com/graphics/2025-ai-data-centers-electricity-prices/?embedded-checkout=true>

⁷ https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5736562

⁸

https://cruie-live-96ca64acab2247eca8a850a7e54b-5b34f62.divio-media.com/documents/CRU2025193_-_Price_Review_Six_-_Final_Determination_-_Summary_Paper.pdf

research gap, by modelling the cost to Irish households of rapid growth of data centres from 2015-2023 and estimated future costs in a range of future scenarios.

The large, remarkably constant, and rising share of total electricity consumption demanded by data centres has consumed almost all additional renewables capacity brought online in recent years (Daly, 2024)⁹. Rather than leading to reduction in wholesale costs for Irish households through a proliferation of low-cost renewables in the Irish electricity market, data centre demand has further embedded a dependence on gas-fired power as a dispatchable energy source required at times of higher and peak demand. The volatile period of geopolitical instability in recent years has led to soaring fossil fuel costs and supply constraints, further exposing Irish households to the costs of gas-fired power dependency, energy crises and constantly high data centre demand.

This report seeks to model and quantify this interaction effect between Ireland's data centre demand profile and a dependence on gas-fired power on wholesale electricity prices. It empirically analyses how data centre demand can shift wholesale prices up the 'merit order curve', forcing gas as a 'price setter' for Irish electricity consumers more than would otherwise be the case in the absence of extremely high data centre energy demand, thereby impacting wholesale prices for Irish society as a whole.

Systemically analysing hundreds of thousands of data points for hourly wholesale prices and residual electricity demand (total demand for electricity not met by available renewables), this report models the approximated wholesale cost effect of data centres in the past – the period of data centre expansion from 2015-2023 – and the future – building a range of scenarios to explore potential projected costs to households from 2025-2034.

Following this introductory section, Section 2 explores the background and conceptual underpinning of research produced for this report. Sections 3 and 4 outline the methodology and provide results for the data centre wholesale cost effect in Ireland from 2015-2023. Sections 5 and 6 provide the methodology and results for future projected costs and scenario exploration. Section 7 provides results for comparative scenarios combining key assumptions from scenarios in Sections 5 and 6. Section 8 summarises key results and concludes.

9

https://www.friendsoftheearth.ie/assets/files/pdf/data_centres_and_the_carbon_budgets_-_prof_hannah_daly_dec_2024.pdf

2. Background

2.1. Gas dependency and marginal pricing

Ireland is one of most gas-reliant countries in the EU to produce electricity (SEAI, 2026¹⁰; Wade et al, 2026¹¹). This dependence on gas creates a cost disparity between times when availability of renewables is sufficient on the Irish electricity market (ISEM) to meet demand, and times when dispatchable, fossil-powered electricity is required. Reliance on gas to produce electricity means the price of natural gas is the key determinant of electricity prices in Ireland (ESB, 2025¹²).

Figure 1 – Electricity generation in Ireland by fuel source, 2024

Source: SEAI, 2026¹³

Electricity markets function on the basis of marginal pricing. In a system known as the ‘merit order’, the cheapest available electricity is chosen to meet demand first by operators – typically this is renewable power. As demand increases, the next cheapest source of electricity continues to meet demand, working up the merit order to electricity derived from more expensive fuels. When this happens and demand is high, the marginal price of wholesale electricity increases – even if renewables form a portion of the demand being met through the market because they are chosen first in the merit order, the price of the most expensive fuel sets that price at that point in time. In simple terms, this fuel at a given point in time is known as the ‘price setter’.

¹⁰ <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/electricity>

¹¹ <https://www.esri.ie/news/irish-electricity-prices-reflect-several-key-trends>

¹²

https://cdn.esb.ie/media/docs/default-source/ask/esb-white-paper-on-electricity-costs-july-2025.pdf?sfvrsn=24d0ae07_5

¹³ <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/electricity>

When demand is low, renewables set the marginal wholesale price of electricity. When demand is higher, at peak times of the day (in evenings, for example, when homes are full and energy is required for cooking, washing, and so on), available renewables cannot meet demand, and dispatchable fossil fuels are required more often – in Ireland, this means gas is often the price setter during these times of day. For context, econometric analysis by Zakeri et al (2023¹⁴) estimates that gas was the marginal price setter in Ireland 44% of the time in 2021.

This merit order concept, crucial as a context to this research, is summarised graphically in Figure 2.

Figure 2 – A graphic representation of merit order operations

Across Europe, similar dynamics exist. In 2022, gas generated just 19% of total power traded in European electricity markets but set prices 55% of the time (Gasparella et al, 2023¹⁵). Modelling undertaken by the European Commission shows that this highly disproportionate price-setting relationship will continue out to 2030, despite (insufficiently) growing renewables capacity (ibid, 2023).

In recent years, in the wake of price shocks during COVID-19 economic constraints and the extraordinary gas price shock following Russia’s invasion of Ukraine in 2022, wholesale electricity prices in Ireland have been higher than pre-crisis levels (see Figure 3 below). Soaring prices in these periods has laid bare the exposure of Irish households, and particularly low-income households for

¹⁴ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352484723013057#appSB>

¹⁵ The Merit Order and Price-Setting Dynamics in European Electricity Markets: A 2022 and 2030 Investigation using METIS (Gasparella et al, 2023)

whom a greater portion of their income is spent on utilities, to the effects of fossil fuel price shocks due to Ireland’s considerable dependence on gas-fired power (SEAI, 2025¹⁶).

Figure 3 – Average daily wholesale electricity prices, 2015-2023

Source: ENTSO-E Transparency Platform¹⁷

2.2. Data centres, gas, and wholesale prices

The interaction effect between gas dependence in the Irish electricity market, and the high and rising share of inflexible data centre demand on the grid, is, in these proportions, unique across Europe. However, disproportionate fossil-fuel price-setting through merit order operations is not unique to Ireland and considering recent developments in the UK and EU on data centre expansion policies, similar relationships could emerge in other places.

The two moving parts of a) how electricity markets govern wholesale electricity prices through a merit order sensitive to demand, and b) that data centres consume a large, stable, and growing share of electricity from the Irish electricity market, could render Ireland over-exposed to price shocks, wholesale cost increases due to peak demand spikes, and, as a general trend, gas as a disproportionate price setter over time.

At times of peak demand, when gas is a price setter for the whole electricity market in Ireland, data centres constitute a remarkably inflexible share of total power consumption. Unlike the power consumption of households or small businesses, which fluctuate considerably at different points in the day, data centre demand in Ireland does not.

Figure 4 demonstrates this demand profile for every hour in the year 2023, standardised against the respective daily average for those hours in each day of that year. We can see that in only 0.001% of

¹⁶ <https://www.seai.ie/sites/default/files/publications/bett-energy-poverty-in-ireland.pdf>

¹⁷ <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>

observations does hourly power consumption by data centres stray beyond 5% of average daily consumption.

Figure 4 – Standardised hourly data centre power consumption profile, 2023

Source: Own calculations; CSO, Table MEC04, 2026¹⁸

Note: X axis represents the 8760 hours in the year 2023, the Y axis represents hourly data centre fluctuation in demand standardised to 1 for each hour within its corresponding day in the year.

This essentially constant consumption profile, alongside a rapidly rising share of total consumption on the grid, means that data centre power consumption is constantly high - a trend borne out in international patterns too (IEA, 2025)¹⁹. **When households consume power together at peak periods of the day, data centres' demand profile acts as a rising floor, raising the level of peak demand on the grid higher, and more often, than it would otherwise be.**

Considering merit order operations, this implies that the inflexibly high share of data centre power consumption means total demand in the Irish electricity market exceeds the availability of low-cost renewables more often, meaning gas sets prices more often. In more technical terms, data centres push Ireland's demand profile further up the merit order curve at a given point in time, more often than a counterfactual scenario where no data centres were present on the island of Ireland.

This is, in simple terms, the conceptual underpinnings for the model produced for this study. The coming sections will provide an overview of the model developed to quantify the 'data centre cost effect' in Irish wholesale electricity prices, and borne by households, from 2015-2023. It will also use this quantitative approach as a basis from which to model a range of scenarios from 2025-2034 to approximate the electricity price increases that may be caused by further rising data centre demand, as well as by the relationship between rising demand and further price shocks, in the future.

¹⁸ <https://data.cso.ie/table/MEC04>

¹⁹ <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/de9dea13-b07d-42c5-a398-d1b3ae17d866/EnergyandAI.pdf>

3. Methodology – modelling the data centre wholesale electricity cost effect, 2015-2023

3.1. Model overview

Public data showing the ‘menu’ of options in the merit order available to system operators at each point in time, at high time resolution, is not available. This study, therefore, simulates and approximates the merit order curve using a variable known as ‘residual demand’ (Do et al, 2016²⁰; Do et al, 2021; Kay et al, 2026²¹; Cludius et al, 2025²²)²³. This is a technical term for total demand minus total available renewables on the grid at a given point in time, i.e. the demand which could not be met by renewable power, and must therefore be met by dispatchable power, typically fossil fuels (gas in the Irish case), further up the merit order curve.

First, a residual demand value for each hour of the day from 2015-2023 is calculated using EirGrid system data (subtracting total ISEM wind generated power from total ISEM demand at each point in time)²⁴. Using very high resolution data from the ENTSO-E Transparency Platform, which provides the wholesale price on the ISEM for each hour in each day from 2015-2023²⁵, we then build a robust residual demand-price relationship for every hour between 6th January 2015 and the end of 2023 (approximately 78,800 data points).

Ordering this large dataset into percentiles, and taking an average wholesale price for each percentile, we can see a clear approximated merit order price curve (Figure 5 below). **When residual demand is high, at times when demand on the grid far outstrips the ability of available renewables capacity to meet this demand, prices are higher.** Much like merit order operations, this curve is non-linear, particularly in the highest percentiles.

²⁰ <https://www.rees-journal.org/articles/rees/pdf/2016/01/rees160045-s.pdf>

²¹ <https://www.dallasfed.org/~media/documents/research/papers/2026/wp2606.pdf>

²² <https://www.oeko.de/oekodoc/2025/2014-610-en.pdf>

²³ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261920316846>

²⁴

<https://www.eirgrid.ie/grid/system-and-renewable-data-reports#System%20and%20Renewable%20Data%20Reports>

²⁵ <https://transparency.entsoe.eu/>

Figure 5 – Residual demand-wholesale price curve (ISEM), 2015-2023

Source: ENTSO-E Transparency Platform; own calculations

3.2. Data centres and residual demand

This proxy for the merit order curve allows us to estimate where price and residual demand meet at a given point in time, and, crucially, where a counterfactual residual demand scenario would be situated on the price curve if data centres were subtracted from total demand.

The first step to achieve this is to produce a counterfactual ‘no data centre’ residual demand time series for each hour from 2015-2023. In official EirGrid analyses, data centre demand on the grid is treated as essentially constant (EirGrid, 2026²⁶). For precision, we start with quarterly average data centre power consumption data from the Central Statistics Office (CSO) in MW (a load unit) and scale to total MWh consumed in a quarter (a flow unit). We divide this total consumption estimate by total days in a quarter for a *daily* MWh estimate. An *hourly shape* is then added to this daily demand profile using the 2023 hourly data centre demand series from the CSO, by calculating ratios of hourly consumption relative to average daily consumption of all data centres for each day in 2023.

For example, the ratio of data centre power demand for each hour on 1st January 2023 relative to *the daily average* of power consumption of data centres *in the same day*, is used for the same respective

²⁶

[https://cms.eirgrid.ie/sites/default/files/publications/AIRAA-2026-2035_Ireland.pdf#:~:text=The%20updated%20methodology%20\(first%20implemented%20in%20the,interconnectors%20as%20well%20as%20energy%20storage%20solutions.](https://cms.eirgrid.ie/sites/default/files/publications/AIRAA-2026-2035_Ireland.pdf#:~:text=The%20updated%20methodology%20(first%20implemented%20in%20the,interconnectors%20as%20well%20as%20energy%20storage%20solutions.)

hours on 1st January in 2015, 2016 and so on. These specific hourly factors are applied for each hour in all 365 days across all years in our time series 2015-2023²⁷.

We then subtract this hourly data centre demand series from our residual demand series 2015-2023, producing a hypothetical demand scenario over time in which there *is no data centre demand* in the ISEM.

3.3. Estimating the data centre wholesale price margin

With our two residual demand series for each hour from 2015-2023 – one based on observed data with data centre demand included, and a counterfactual series with estimated hourly data centre demand removed – we now move to estimate the gap between the two series at all hourly time points on the residual demand curve. Figure 6 below illustrates the methodological approach, where the gap on the Y-axis, where the two residual demand points meet the price curve, represents the price gap at a given point in time.

Figure 6 – A stylised residual demand-price curve to demonstrate data centre wholesale cost margin estimation method

For each individual year in our study, we rank order residual demand values (with data centres still included) into percentiles. We disaggregate by each year so as to maintain within-year price regimes, and not have the method distorted by 2022 wholesale electricity price spikes, for example.

Using the threshold values for each percentile (i.e. the point at which a value moves from one percentile to another), we then repeat the same process for our hypothetical residual demand series

²⁷ 29th February in leap years used 28th February hourly factors.

without data centres, grouping them into percentiles based on their hypothetical position on the residual demand-price curve.

Let's take Figure 6 above as an example. With data centres on the grid, at this point in time (say 7pm-8pm on 20th April 2018) the residual demand value is such that it is ranked in the 75th percentile. If we subtract data centre electricity demand, it falls to the 45th percentile²⁸. Crucially, we know the average wholesale cost for all residual demand values for each percentile within each year – but not for our hypothetical residual demand series without data centre energy consumption. So how do we estimate this?

At the 75th percentile for this point in time, the wholesale cost might be €150 per MWh. By taking the average wholesale costs of the 45th percentile of the residual demand series with data centres included – say €100 per MWh – and assigning this to the hypothetical residual demand value without data centres for that percentile (45th), we calculate the ***hypothetical difference on the residual demand-price curve*** between two residual demand series (with and without data centres) at the ***same point in time***. This process is repeated for each hour within each year from 2015-2023. The *average of the differences* is taken as the annual estimate of data centre margin within ISEM wholesale electricity costs in € per MWh terms²⁹.

It should be noted that all wholesale price data is in nominal terms and no price adjustment is included here. We also assume 100% wholesale electricity cost pass-through by electricity suppliers to households. This is a methodological choice to streamline the modelling approach, as estimating cost pass-through via large electricity suppliers with limited public data is a time-intensive research endeavour. It also has some indicative support in research, given that the energy component (i.e. wholesale costs) of retail bills in Ireland remains three times higher than actual wholesale costs in Ireland (as of 2024) (IEA, 2025³⁰).

²⁸ This fall is never this large in reality at a given point in time but is exaggerated here to illuminate the method.

²⁹ Whilst other methodological approaches may be available to approach this question – econometric analysis, for example - the approach adopted here is useful in that it allows for granular capturing of within-day and within-year hourly fluctuations in residual demand profiles, and related price effects, in a way that more linear regression models may smooth over.

³⁰ <https://iea.blob.core.windows.net/assets/76ad6eac-2aa6-4c55-9a55-b8dc0dba9f9e/Renewables2025.pdf>

4. Results - modelling the data centre wholesale electricity cost margin, 2015-2023

4.1.2015-2023–wholesale price impactsof data centres

Through the modelling approach outlined in the above methodology section, the average household will have been expected to pay a cumulative **€360** in additional wholesale costs in household bills between 2015-2023 due to the data centre price effect.

Almost three-quarters (73%) of this estimated cumulative cost – **about €263** – which has been borne by the average household came in the years 2021-2023, during a prolonged and complex energy price shock. This is a central result in this report. It indicates the direct wholesale cost exposure of Irish households to the interaction effect between rising and inflexible data centre demand, and reliance on gas-fired power, at periods of extreme price volatility.

The average annual price effect of data centres pushing the ISEM residual demand profile further up the price curve, in € per MWh terms, are shown in Table 1. In essence, these results can be read as the approximated differences, per unit of power consumed, on the residual demand-price curve within each year 2015-2023. In other words, for every MWh of power consumed by households in that year, these are the estimated data centre margins in the wholesale cost components of their bill³¹.

Table 1 – Average annual data centre wholesale price effect, per MWh (2015-2023)

Year	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Average Data Centre Price Effect, €/MWh	5.2	1.5	1.7	3.2	5.02	5.1	15.03	33.03	16.7

Using Eurostat data to determine total final residential energy consumption over time (Eurostat, 2026)³², and Eurostat data on total Irish households (Eurostat, 2026)³³, we can estimate (Table 2) the additional wholesale costs incurred by households based on average power consumption per household in each year. Using past CSO data on total average residential electricity bills from 2015-2023, we can see this additional cost expressed in terms of the share of total average consumer bills in each year, and cumulatively from 2015-2023.

³¹ Wholesale costs are, of course, not the totality of household electricity bills, which also include grid charges, supplier margins, the PSO levy, and other core cost components.

³² https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_d_hhq_custom_20448884/default/table

³³ [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfst_hhnhtych\\$defaultview/default/table](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/lfst_hhnhtych$defaultview/default/table)

Table 2 – Total estimated additional data centre driven wholesale costs (€) incurred by average household within each year (2015-2023)

	Cumulative total (2015-2023)	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Additional wholesale costs incurred by average household (€)	360.24	23.63	6.67	7.72	14.00	21.54	23.26	66.82	130.16	66.44
Estimated average household electricity bill (€) ³⁴	12,406.69	1,367.32	1,251.50	1,238.62	1,275.89	1,214.08	1,296.64	1,425.09	1,527.74	1,809.82
Additional data centre wholesale costs as share of average household bills	2.9%	1.7%	0.5%	0.6%	1.1%	1.8%	1.8%	4.7%	8.5%	3.7%

In the earlier years of this study, the share of average household bills comprised by the estimated data centre wholesale cost margin is smaller, but not insignificant. With the onset of rising gas price shock in the early 2020s, coupled with rapidly rising, constant and inflexible data centre demand on the grid, the approximated share of household bills comprised by the data centre cost margin increases significantly.

Scaling this average annual and cumulative data centre effect up to gross total households costs, between 2015 and 2023 all households in the Irish state have paid an estimated **€715.3m** in additional wholesale electricity costs due to the presence of data centres in Ireland (of which **€271.3m** was in 2022 alone, the peak year of wholesale electricity price spikes due to the Russia-Ukraine war).

Given that low income households also spend a greater share of their incomes on electricity³⁵ (and other basic needs), the estimated data centre cost effect is regressive in nature. Table 3 below

³⁴ Average household electricity bills 2015-2023 are estimated by dividing total aggregate national residential bills data (CSO, 2026 – Table 4A, Trends in Metered Electricity and Gas Bills 2023 series) by total households (Eurostat, 2026). So as to not inflate the ‘data centre share’ of bills, the universal subsidies provided through the Electricity Costs Emergency Benefits Scheme (€400 in 2022, €550 in 2023) have been re-added to estimated average annual electricity bills.

³⁵ Lowest income quintile spent 6% of total household budget on electricity in 2023, compared to 2% for the highest income quintile (Household Budget Survey, 2023).

disaggregates the gross average data centre price effect indicated in Table 2 by income quintiles³⁶. Often used to assess income inequality between social groups, these income quintiles take total households in the Republic of Ireland and organise them in five equally populated groups by income. According to the 2022-2023 Household Budget Survey³⁷, for example, households in the lowest (1st) income quintile had average household spending of roughly €23,100³⁸, whilst the highest income group (5th quintile) spent over €91,370 in that year (this gives a quintile inequality ratio of 3.95).

Table 3 – Estimated annual data centre cost effect (€) households, by income quintile (2015-2023)

	Cumulative total, € (2015-2023)	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
1st quintile	286.42	18.79	5.30	6.14	11.13	17.13	18.49	53.12	103.49	52.83
2nd quintile	319.75	20.97	5.92	6.85	12.43	19.12	20.65	59.31	115.53	58.97
3rd quintile	372.63	24.44	6.90	7.99	14.48	22.28	24.06	69.12	134.64	68.73
4th quintile	394.96	25.91	7.31	8.47	15.35	23.62	25.50	73.26	142.70	72.84
5th quintile	428.08	28.08	7.92	9.17	16.64	25.60	27.64	79.40	154.67	78.95
Gross data centre price effect (average)	360.24	23.63	6.67	7.72	14.00	21.54	23.26	66.82	130.16	66.44

³⁶ Total electricity consumption per income quintile is calculated by taking the share of each quintile of total electricity consumption in the Household Budget Survey, and applying these shares to estimates (own calculations) of average residential final electricity consumption per household (Eurostat data). The annual data centre price effect parameter in Table 2 is then multiplied by annual energy consumption by quintile over time to produce estimates in Table 3.

³⁷ <https://www.cso.ie/en/releasesandpublications/ep/p-hbs/householdbudgetsurvey2022-2023/keyfindings/>

³⁸ The HBS was carried out from October 2022 to October 2023.

5. Methodology and results – exploring data centre cost impact in a range of future scenarios (2025-2034)

The conceptual basis for modelling future cost impacts is based on the relationship between residual demand and wholesale price, expressed as the residual demand-price curve, outlined in Section 3. Whilst results in Section 4 estimate these costs on the basis of observed data, **new data centres will continue to come online in Ireland throughout the 2020s and 2030s under current policy arrangements, in a world beset by extreme energy market volatility, and a lagging transition to a sustainable, decarbonised economy.**

In essence, the interaction between these dynamics – rising data centre share of total electricity demand, wholesale electricity price volatility, and the green transition – could have significant impacts on how data centres impact ISEM wholesale prices into the future.

This section, therefore, outlines the methodology and assumptions used to model stylised scenarios which could either intensify, or relieve, the wholesale price impact of data centres and the residual demand-price relationship.

Scenario 1 sets a baseline for future projections based on EirGrid expectations of future electricity demand (across society and of data centres in particular). **Scenario 2** explores how a greater or lesser quantity of renewables on the grid impacts these costs. **Scenario 3** explores how the estimated data centre price impact changes in the context of a hypothetical future price shock. Later we layer these assumptions to contrast Comparative Scenarios using a range of these assumptions together.

Price data in these scenarios are based on nominal values from 2015-2023 and no bespoke price adjustment (to account for inflation) has been applied. This is largely due to the role of energy prices in determining the rate of inflation, and accounting for this feedback effect has been excluded to simplify the modelling approach.

5.1. Scenario 1 (Baseline) method: Projections of the data centre wholesale cost effect in three demand scenarios (2025-2034)

To approximate how data centres may impact wholesale prices and household bills in the future, we must have a projection of future levels of demand – of society at large and of data centres in particular – alongside a projection of future wind generation and wholesale prices.

The time frame of 2025-2034 was chosen for this period of analysis because plentiful data for estimating future values of key variables are provided in the ‘All-Island Resource Adequacy Assessment 2025-2034’ produced by EirGrid³⁹. Three demand scenarios – low, median, and high – are formed through a range of assumptions such as electrification of energy systems in Ireland, renewable capacity generation, economic growth, and data centre demand growth, among others.

Estimates for total average annual demand in the ISEM, total estimated renewables capacity, and total annual data centre consumption from the ‘Adequacy Assessment’ supplementary data are used to calculate three residual demand pathways under low, median and high assumptions from 2025 to 2034.

³⁹ <https://cms.eirgrid.ie/sites/default/files/publications/AIRAA-2025-2034.pdf>

Figure 7 – EirGrid low, median, and high demand trajectories out to 2034

Source: [EirGrid AIAA 2025-2034 \(2025\)](#)

EirGrid data for average annual load under each of their three demand scenarios are transformed into an hourly time series for each hour in the year 2025-2034 using an hourly demand profile shape (i.e. hourly demand shares of a total year) from past data (2015-2023). The same approach is adopted for moving average annual data centre load estimates to an hourly time series.

Total wind generation is estimated based on assumptions rooted in Ireland’s Climate Action Plan but is expressed as capacity – the maximum capacity to generate electricity - not as a flow unit (such as MWh). Using the same hourly renewable rating factors for onshore and offshore wind employed by EirGrid in their modelling (EirGrid, 2025⁴⁰), we estimate total generated power from EirGrid’s onshore and offshore wind capacity estimates in each year of our future time series and again use 2015-2023 past generation profiles to provide an hourly resolution of the full time series.

These calculated hourly time series from 2025-2034 allow us to calculate two residual demand time series, with and without data centres, for the low, median and high demand EirGrid scenarios.

The method of pooling data points in percentiles by rank order of residual demand to estimate difference in relative positions along the residual demand price curve adopted for the historical analysis (2015-2023) is not possible here as no future price data exists. Moreover, stochastic and fundamentally volatile nature of electricity prices (Gudkov and Ignatieva, 2021⁴¹) in the future is such that prediction of future prices is fraught with limitation.

As such all wholesale price estimates for Scenario 1 are understood to be approximations based on past trends and the relationship between residual demand and wholesale prices – it should be expected that these trends change in the future.

⁴⁰ https://cms.eirgrid.ie/sites/default/files/publications/AIRAA-2026-2035_Inputs-and-Assumptions-Ireland.pdf

⁴¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0140988321001651>

Wholesale prices are approximated⁴² for Scenario 1 through an econometric approach, for all low, median and high EirGrid demand scenarios with and without data centres, using a log-linear regression model where log wholesale prices are the dependent variable, and the regressor is residual demand. We use the extremely high resolution data from our 2015-2023 residual demand modelling (price data from ENTSO-E, demand data from EirGrid) to estimate the log-linear coefficient on the basis of over 78,000 observations. The logarithm of wholesale price data is taken to reflect the non-linear, even exponential, shape of the residual demand-price curve.

Though total variation in wholesale prices is not adequately explained by residual demand as a *sole* regressor⁴³, this is a reasonable approach to *approximating cost trends* from past data due to a) the high statistical significance of the model, and b) the robust conceptual foundation linking wholesale prices and residual demand as a proxy for the merit order curve. It is acknowledged, of course, that future prices can easily stray from past trends, driven by any number of variables – we attempt to model this volatility in the price shock scenario in this report.

After approximating wholesale prices for each hour in our three EirGrid demand scenarios, and residual demand series with and without data centres for each of the three EirGrid demand pathways, we can calculate the approximated wholesale price difference at each point in time. Taking an annual average of these hourly differences, much like the method outlined in Section 3, gives us a € per MWh wholesale cost differential attributed to data centres by moving residual demand further up the price curve.

Scenario 1 outlined in this section functions as a baseline scenario for our future data centre cost estimates, with additional assumptions made in Scenarios 2 and 3 to explore how wholesale cost differentials between data centre and non-data centre scenarios change in a range of conditions.

5.2. Results – Scenario 1 (Baseline)

Results in Scenario 1 estimate the data centre wholesale electricity price effect, driven by the pressure placed by data centres on the residual demand-price curve, for the years 2025-2034 under three different energy demand scenarios – low, median, and high.

Moving through each demand scenario from low to high based on EirGrid assumptions, total energy consumption increases alongside total data centre power consumption. In higher demand scenarios, however, the share of data centre power demand in the Republic of Ireland (as opposed to the total ISEM demand) increases. For context, Table 4 shows the share of total electricity demand of data centres of total power demand in Ireland based on EirGrid projections, peaking at around 30% of total consumption around 2030 in the high demand scenario.

⁴² The regression model used here is not claimed as a perfect predictor of notoriously volatile wholesale prices which are so tied to the price of gas. It is, however, given the scale of the dataset on which the model is predicated and the amount of data points approximated by it in the 2025-2034 scenarios, a highly statistically significant (p-value < 0.001) a useful, if imperfect, approximation of prices.

⁴³ $R^2 = 0.12$

Table 4 – Data centre share of total electricity consumption (RoI) in EirGrid demand scenarios

	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
Data Centre % Total Demand - Low	0.193	0.200	0.205	0.209	0.215	0.219	0.223	0.226	0.229	0.230	0.232
Data Centre % Total Demand - Median	0.207	0.219	0.229	0.234	0.241	0.245	0.250	0.253	0.254	0.254	0.253
Data Centre % Total Demand - High	0.228	0.255	0.269	0.278	0.289	0.296	0.300	0.299	0.297	0.294	0.292

Source: EirGrid AIAA 2025-2034 (2025)

The per unit data centre effect on wholesale electricity in prices for each of our three demand scenarios is illustrated in Figure 8. The rising estimated price effect from 2025-2029 reflects rising data centre demand on the grid over time, pushing total residual demand further up the cost curve. EirGrid demand scenarios, however, assume a significant leap in renewable energy capacity between 2029-2030 (from 2,598 MW total wind capacity in 2029 to 3,587 in 2030, for example, alongside a rapid increase in solar power). Based on the modelling approach in this report, this additional renewable capacity decreases residual demand significantly, triggering a move down the residual demand-price curve, making gas less likely to be a price setter as often, and dampening the per unit data centre wholesale price effect.

Figure 8 – Data centre wholesale price effect, € per MWh, 2025-2034

In order to calculate the gross costs for the average household across our three demand scenarios, we must estimate average residential electricity consumption in each year 2025-2034 for each scenario. To do this, we take total residential electricity consumption for the EirGrid median demand scenario and divide by total estimated households 2025-2034⁴⁴ to estimate MWh per household per

⁴⁴ Total households from 2025-2034 are modelled by taking the Eurostat Labour Force Survey time series of [total households from 2015-2023](#), and applying a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) to 2023 value for 2024-2034 values (for use in the 2025-2034 series) calculated from [CSO future population projections](#) (Table PEC19). The mid-range (Method 2) population projections are taken as a time series, the natural logarithm of values from 2024-2034 are taken, and the slope of these values against time is calculated to estimate a CAGR (taking the exponent of this slope coefficient, minus 1) – this CAGR value 2024-2034 is 0.85%.

year across our scenario period. A ratio of the median demand scenario is calculated for low and high demand scenarios, and this same ratio is applied to the median scenario MWh per household.

With these inputs, we can calculate the gross annual data centre price effect per household across the 2025-2034 projection period, and the cumulative costs per household in that time. Table 5 summarises these results.

Table 5 - Annual and cumulative data centre price effect, € per year per average household – Scenario 1

Scenario	Cumulative total	Annual data centre price effect (€ per year per household)									
		2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EirGrid LD ⁴⁵ scenario	295.16	33.88	34.06	34.11	33.79	33.53	28.25	26.59	25.01	23.69	22.27
EirGrid MD scenario	460.9	43.08	46.99	50.18	51.87	53.21	46.23	44.89	43.29	41.62	39.54
EirGrid HD scenario	663.75	55.4	64.42	71.56	76.21	80.19	69.89	66.91	63.17	59.81	56.2

The average household in Ireland can expect to pay an approximated **€295, €461, and €644 cumulatively across 2025-2034** in the three demand scenarios (low, median and high) due to rising data centre presence on the grid, forcing wholesale prices further up the residual demand-price curve. These estimates are also based on past wholesale price trends (2015-2023), which will continue to be volatile and unpredictable into the future, and the assumed EirGrid renewables investment pathway. Should these conditions change from the assumptions input in Scenario 1, the approximated cost exposure to households can change considerably (see results in Scenarios 2 and 3).

Scaling the per household averages across the three demand scenarios up to a gross cost for all projected households in the state from 2025-2034, the gross national data centre effect could be as high as **€633 million, €991 million, and €1.43 billion** cumulatively across the ten year scenario period, for the low, median and high demand scenarios respectively. This is a significant quantity of foregone household spending that would be committed to wholesale electricity costs through electricity suppliers (assuming 100% wholesale cost pass-through), instead of to other essential household commodities.

Importantly from a data centre policy perspective, there are significant differences to the estimated household cost impacts that intensify in the high demand scenarios. In 2025, the ratio between the price parameters of € per MWh (Figure 8 above) of the high and low demand scenarios is 1.49. This climbs to more than 2.02 in later years, representing an *escalating, non-linear wholesale price effect* endured by households should data centres be allowed to consume around 30% of all power in Ireland by the 2030s. **In other words, the cost effect to Irish households in the high data centre demand scenario, escalates over time relative to other scenarios, which indicates a hazard for households to unfettered data centre expansion in the future.**

⁴⁵ LD = low demand, MD = median demand, HD = high demand

5.3. Scenario 2 method: Different renewable generation capacity pathways

Scenario 2 explores how data centres impact household bills in conditions where renewable energy pathways change. More renewable power on the ISEM is important for the modelling exercise in this study, as it can lower residual demand at a given point in time, reducing the likelihood of gas as the price setter, and thereby moving down the price curve and suppressing possible data centre cost effects. In simple terms, Scenario 2 investigates the degree to which different renewables development pathways impact this data centre cost effect.

The baseline EirGrid scenarios for low, median and high demand pathways (Scenario 1) all assume a given amount of renewable electricity capacity being added to the grid over time. These assumptions are rooted in the Irish Climate Action Plan additional renewables capacity targets but are ultimately less optimistic and assume these targets are broadly missed until around 2034 (EirGrid, 2024⁴⁶).

Therefore, alongside the EirGrid assumptions, we also explore renewable capacity pathways informed by the SEAI's With Existing Measures (WEM) and With Additional Measures (WAM) pathway assumptions (SEAI, 2025⁴⁷). WEM estimates likely renewable capacity into the future under *existing policy commitments and delivery* by government and is more pessimistic than the baseline EirGrid assumptions. For most of the time series, WAM estimates reflect more optimistic assumptions where additional policy achieves a quicker expansion of renewables capacity earlier, though is finally surpassed by EirGrid assumptions in 2034 (the only year in which EirGrid assumptions are larger than WAM). **Including WAM as a renewables pathway, therefore, demonstrates the effect of earlier build out of renewables, suppressing the data centre cost effect earlier and more consistently across the scenario period 2025-2034 (see Table 5 below).**

The SEAI (2025) provides onshore wind, offshore wind, and solar capacity estimates for WEM and WAM pathways for 2025 and 2030⁴⁸. We assume that capacity grows between these poles linearly and missing values for years between 2025-2030 and 2030-2034 are interpolated/extrapolated.

Table 6 summarises the different renewable capacity estimates based on these pathways and used as inputs for Scenario 2. Again, these capacity units (GW and MW) are scaled to MWh using EirGrid's hourly renewable rating factors⁴⁹. The hourly shape across each year for wind energy is calculated from past data from 2015-2023. Due to the relative absence of solar power in Ireland in the past, and therefore the lack of a robust hourly time series of solar generation from EirGrid system data, the 2025 hourly shape of solar generation across a year (sourced from EirGrid system data to account for seasonal and within day fluctuations which are crucial in the variance of generated solar power) is used for all years 2025-2034.

⁴⁶ <https://cms.eirgrid.ie/sites/default/files/publications/AIRAA-2025-2034-Input-Assumptions-Ireland.pdf>

⁴⁷ <https://www.seai.ie/sites/default/files/publications/National-Energy-Projections-Report-2025.pdf>

⁴⁸ <https://www.seai.ie/sites/default/files/publications/National-Energy-Projections-Report-2025.pdf>

⁴⁹ 0.46 for offshore wind, 0.3 for onshore wind, and 0.11 for solar power.

Table 6 – Three renewable capacity pathways used in Scenario 3 modelling of data centre cost impact on wholesale electricity prices under different conditions

Year	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EirGrid Projections - onshore & offshore wind and solar										
MW capacity	2371	2572	2772	3003	3255	4333	4853	5358	5880	6408
SEAI WEM adjusted projections - onshore & offshore wind and solar										
MW capacity	2272	2592	2912	3247	3604	4192	4549	4907	5264	5622
SEAI WAM adjusted projections - onshore & offshore wind and solar										
MW capacity	2371	2774	3177	3595	4035	4706	5146	5586	6027	6467

5.4. Results – Scenario 2: Renewables development pathways

Results in this section explore the effect of different renewables pathways on the data centre wholesale cost effect. As detailed in the methodology section above, greater renewables capacity can increase the availability of renewable energy, pushing residual demand further down the cost curve with gas setting prices comparatively less often than a baseline scenario.

Conversely, a renewables generation pathway that undershoots EirGrid predictions (the With Existing Measures pathway) would increase this tightness, with higher data centre demand placed on the grid over time and less renewables available to satisfy this demand, thereby moving up the residual demand-cost curve.

Table 7 - Data centre wholesale cost effect parameters – low, median and high electricity demand scenarios – EirGrid, WEM, WAM Renewables Pathways, € per MWh

€ per MWh Data Centre Wholesale Price Effect - High Demand Scenario - EirGrid, WEM, WAM Renewables Pathways										
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EG	13.08	14.9	16.52	17.57	18.47	16.17	15.53	14.76	14.05	13.28
WEM	13.08	14.9	16.07	16.72	17.22	16.59	16.44	16.07	15.76	15.38
WAM	13.08	14.4	15.26	15.64	15.87	15.06	14.7	14.16	13.69	13.18
€ per MWh Data Centre Wholesale Price Effect - Median Demand Scenario - EirGrid, WEM, WAM Renewables Pathways										
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EG	10.57	11.54	12.35	12.84	13.25	11.58	11.27	10.91	10.52	10.03
WEM	10.78	11.5	12.01	12.23	12.36	11.88	11.93	11.86	11.8	11.6
WAM	10.57	11.1	11.41	11.44	11.39	10.79	10.67	10.46	10.25	9.94
€ per MWh Data Centre Wholesale Price Effect - Low Demand Scenario - EirGrid, WEM, WAM Renewables Pathways										
	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EG	8.77	9	9.22	9.3	9.37	8.02	7.65	7.29	6.95	6.6
WEM	8.94	8.97	8.97	8.86	8.74	8.22	8.09	7.92	7.79	7.63
WAM	8.77	8.66	8.52	8.29	8.06	7.47	7.24	6.99	6.78	6.54

Looking at the per unit data centre wholesale cost parameters summarised in Table 7, some clear trends are available. The EirGrid renewables pathway (EG) shows some of the highest data centre cost effects up to 2030, when a significant jump in renewables capacity is assumed. This additional capacity then acts to suppress the € per MWh cost effect of data centres after 2030. **In the ensuing period 2030-2034, therefore, the WEM pathway – assumed to best represent existing government policy trajectories – creates the highest cost in each year in all demand scenarios.**

In the WAM scenario, the earlier period 2025-2030 assumes a gradual, early build out of additional renewables capacity, suppressing the data centre cost earlier by moving residual demand further down the cost curve. **It is for this reason – the earlier buildout of additional renewables under WAM – that the cumulative estimated costs for households (see WAM results in Table 8 below) is the lowest across all scenarios.** This underlines the importance of ambitious and sustained renewables development pathways to offset the interaction effects of gas dependence and inflexible data centre demand analysed in this report.

The variance of the development of renewables in this scenario is crucial for the modelling in this report. For almost all demand scenarios, for all renewables pathways, in each year in our future scenario period, the scale of renewables development is insufficient to outpace the growth in electricity consumption by data centres (and Irish society), thus maintaining a dependence on gas (i.e. residual demand remains positive).

However, for the lowest demand scenario, for the EirGrid baseline and WAM renewables development pathways, annual average residual demand (including data centres) falls below 0 in

2033 and 2034⁵⁰⁵¹. In other words, renewables development is sufficient to displace a reliance on gas as a dispatchable source of energy. The assumptions at which these qualitative change in results occurs, however, are unlikely. Existing policy pathways do not indicate that a sufficiently rapid and ambitious renewables capacity expansion is underway (at least to the scale assumed in the EirGrid and modelled WAM pathways in this report), or that data centre demand will stay at the lowest bounds.

This core result underlines that *demand side reductions in data centre energy consumption* continue to be the core driver of reduced data centre driven costs, as represented by the differences between the three demand scenarios. **It also strongly suggests that mitigating the data centre cost effect into the future requires both a drastic expansion in renewables capacity and placing limits on data centre energy consumption.**

⁵⁰ The log price-residual demand model in this report still calculates a data centre price effect, however this should be interpreted merely as a move down the merit order curve model, not explained by gas-fired power as a driver.

⁵¹ For many hourly data points in these narrow scenario assumptions, residual demand stays positive, but the annual average is negative - in general, the role of gas in price setting with data centres on the grid is consistently displaced by available renewables.

Table 8 – Annual and cumulative data centre price effect – Low, Median and High Electricity Demand Scenarios – EirGrid (Scenario 1 - Baseline), WEM, WAM Renewables Pathways

Annual and cumulative data centre price effect, € per year per average household – Scenario 3 - High Demand Scenario											
	Cumulative Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EG	663.7	55.4	64.42	71.56	76.21	80.19	69.89	66.91	63.17	59.81	56.2
WEM	681.04	56.49	64.15	69.59	72.55	74.79	71.7	70.81	68.76	67.11	65.07
WAM	623.16	55.4	61.92	66.11	67.82	68.89	65.08	63.33	60.57	58.3	55.74
Annual and cumulative data centre price effect, € per year per average household – Scenario 3 - Median Demand Scenario											
	Cumulative Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EG	460.9	43.08	46.99	50.18	51.87	53.21	46.23	44.89	43.29	41.62	39.54
WEM	473.04	43.93	46.79	48.8	49.41	49.64	47.43	47.5	47.08	46.68	45.76
WAM	433.44	43.08	45.16	46.37	46.23	45.74	43.07	42.49	41.52	40.57	39.21
Annual and cumulative data centre price effect, € per year per average household – Scenario 3 - Low Demand Scenario ⁵²											
	Cumulative Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EG	295.2	33.88	34.06	34.11	33.79	33.53	28.25	26.59	25.01	23.69	22.27
WEM	301.7	34.55	33.92	33.17	32.19	31.28	28.98	28.12	27.19	26.56	25.75
WAM	277.8	33.88	32.74	31.52	30.12	28.83	26.32	25.17	23.99	23.1	22.09

Looking at the cost effect in gross terms for households, annually and cumulatively across our scenario period (Table 8), the WAM renewables pathway sees the lowest cumulative data centre wholesale cost effects from 2025-2034 in all demand scenarios. **Conversely, the WEM pathway, which best reflects current policy trajectories, sees the highest cumulative costs for households over the same period.**

In gross terms, the cumulative costs over this period also rise as the data centre share of total electricity demand rises across the three demand scenarios. Yet within demand scenarios, changes in renewable energy pathways have only a marginal impact on costs. This indicates that the scale of overall data centre demand remains the biggest driver of additional costs that could be incurred by households in the projected 2025-2034 period.

The lowest cumulative costs modelled here – **€278** from 2025-2034 in the low demand scenario and more ambitious WAM renewables pathway – still represent a significant additional cost for household bills in this period. However, it is significantly lower than the highest modelled cost, where

⁵²The years in which average annual residual demand falls below zero are highlighted (EG and WAM, 2023 and 2024), where renewables capacity is sufficient to consistently displace the data centre price effect modelled in this paper. These four data points are a feature of the residual demand-price curve, and should not be interpreted as a gas-fired power interaction with data centre demand.

WEM renewables pathway in the highest demand scenario can see cumulative additional data centre wholesale price costs for households of **€681**.

This **€403** range between the highest and lowest modelled costs in Scenario 2 again foregrounds the significance of policy options in mitigating the approximated data centre wholesale cost effect in Ireland into the future – **only by limiting overall data centre demand, and expanding renewables capacity, under the projected wholesale cost regime approximated for this study, can policy suppress the cost effects of data centres. Undershooting renewables targets, and allowing excessive growth of data centre energy consumption, can lead to significant additional costs for households into the future.**

5.5. Scenario 3 method: Hypothetical wholesale electricity price shock in 2030-2031

As highlighted throughout this report, the relationship between growing and inflexible data centre demand, and an electricity market dependent on gas-fired power, could leave Ireland over-exposed to fossil fuel price shocks. Mounting geopolitical instability has forced two exceptional energy price shocks in just five years. As such, it is not implausible that such instability may be a feature of energy markets for the foreseeable future.

In Scenario 3, therefore, we investigate how data centres impact household prices in the event of a hypothetical fossil fuel price shock across 2030 and 2031. This is a simple and stylised scenario to reveal trends and provide estimates of the household impact of the data centre cost effect in the event of a fossil fuel price shock, which can be assessed comparatively across a range of data centre demand scenarios.

Starting with results from Scenario 1, where we have estimated two residual demand series with and without data centres for each hour 2025-2034 for three demand trajectories (low, median and high), and corresponding wholesale price differentials, we assume a price shock beginning on 1st January 2030 rolls out linearly for 180 days. The peak of this shock is determined using real wholesale price data for the extraordinary price shock of summer 2022 (from June to September)⁵³. Figure 9 below highlights the scale of this peak from this period (the gap between June and September 2022 on the Y-axis) chosen as a stylised input for designing the peak price point in this hypothetical shock scenario. Given the extraordinary nature of this shock in 2022, we extend the shock implementation period to 180 days, instead of the approximately 90 days during which it transpired in 2022, to account for a slightly more gradual shock in the future.

⁵³ Data is smoothed by calculating a 30-day rolling average of daily wholesale prices for this period. The difference in the values of the natural logarithms of the wholesale price on 1st June 2022 and 3rd September (the peak price in the series) is taken and then divided by 180 days to give a compound daily growth rate to simulate linear price increases reaching the same relative peak of this three month shock period in the first 180 days of 2030 in our stylised price shock scenario.

Figure 9 – 30 day rolling average daily ISEM wholesale prices and indicative shock period (June-September 2022)

Source: ENTSO-E Transparency Platform; own calculations

In this scenario, after six months of consistent wholesale price increases in 2030, prices fall for the next six months until 31st December 2030, but they do not reach pre-shock trend levels. To reflect lingering wholesale electricity cost inflation, as transpired throughout 2023, wholesale prices remain 20% higher than pre-trend levels all throughout 2031. Wholesale prices return to pre-trend levels in 2032 in Scenario 3.

Conceptually, different positions along the residual demand-price curve of our data centre and no data centre residual demand series at a given point in time means different sensitivities to fossil fuel price shocks. In other words, if at a given point in time our time series for residual demand without data centres is further down the price curve, it is assumed that gas is setting prices less often, as residual demand is lower. To approximate these differing sensitivities to the above price shock of our data centre and no data centre residual demand series, we calculate the respective slopes of the projected residual demand – wholesale price data for 2030 (see Scenario 1) for data centre and no data centre series and then take the ratio of the slopes⁵⁴.

5.6. Results – Scenario 3: Price shock 2030-31

Whilst Scenario 1 estimates the data centre price effect in Ireland based on modelled wholesale prices that reflect trends (2015-2023), wholesale electricity prices are extremely difficult to predict with any certainty, particularly in the context of Irish gas-fired power dependence and rising geopolitical instability affecting the world’s foremost fossil fuel producers.

⁵⁴ Using this method, we assume the no-data centre residual demand series in our Scenario 2 price shock is less sensitive to the price shock than the residual demand series with data centre demand included by a factor of 0.77.

To explore the possible effects of a further price shock⁵⁵, therefore, results in this section show the data centre wholesale price effect of a stylised wholesale electricity price shock based on the June-September 2022 price spike.

Based on our stylised price shock 2030-2031, the average household in Ireland can expect to pay **cumulatively €338, €520 and €739 in additional costs** respectively across our three demand scenarios due to the data centre wholesale price effect from 2025-2034.

Isolating the effects of the price shock in 2030 and 2031 versus our baseline Scenario 1 projections, this represents an additional **€32, €44 and €54 for the low, median and high demand** scenarios respectively in 2030, and a further **€11, €16 and €20** in 2031 in these scenarios. In total then across the price shock period 2030-2031, households would bear an additional **€43, €59 and €76 – a 78%, 65%, and 55%**⁵⁶ increase compared to scenario 1 respectively – across the three demand scenarios in electricity costs due to the presence and scale of data centre energy demand.

Cumulatively for all households in the Irish state during our scenario period 2025-2034 this equates to a modelled €726 million, €1.11 billion, €1.6 billion across the three demand scenarios (low, median and high). This means the cumulative gross price shock equates to an additional €93m, €129m, and €164m in a data centre cost effect versus the Scenario 1 baseline.

Table 9 - Annual and cumulative data centre price effect, € per year per average household – Scenario 3

	Annual data centre price effect (€ per year per household) – Scenario 1 + price shock 2030/31										
	Cumulative Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
EirGrid low demand scenario	338.1	33.9	34.1	34.1	33.8	33.5	60.6	37.1	25	23.7	22.3
EirGrid median demand scenario	520.3	43.1	47	50.2	51.9	53.2	90	60.5	43.3	41.6	39.5
EirGrid high demand scenario	739.2	55.4	64.4	71.6	76.2	80.2	124.7	87.7	63.2	59.8	56.2

To be clear, these estimates are not simply the effect of the simulated price shock itself, which affects wholesale electricity prices in general. These are the approximated *additional costs to households*, if a price shock of this design transpired in 2030 and 2031, which can be attributable to the wholesale cost pressure of data centres specifically, in these three demand scenarios.

Aside from the wholesale price shock in general, which we assume in stylised scenarios is driven by a moderate fossil fuel price spike, the wholesale price difference in € per MWh between our data centre and no data centre residual demand series is also a driver (see Figure 10 below). As outlined in the methodology section for Scenario 3, the hourly residual demand series which includes data centre demand is more sensitive to the stylised wholesale price increases in 2030 and 2031 because of its position further up the residual demand-price curve in that year, where residual demand is higher and gas – which in this scenario has been hypothetically subjected to a price shock - would be setting prices more often.

⁵⁵ A methodological choice is made in this report to not attempt to model the energy price shock triggered by the US-Israeli war against Iran, as the price effects and related data are not sufficiently clear or available at the time of writing.

⁵⁶ The decline in magnitude by the higher denominators in higher demand scenarios.

Figure 10 – Data centre wholesale price effect, € per MWh, 2025-2034 – Scenario 3

6. Results - Comparative scenarios

6.1. Comparative scenarios outline

To further draw out the interaction effects between the scenario results in the above section, here we investigate the data centre wholesale cost effect of the combined assumptions modelled in the range of scenarios above.

This report investigates the scale of the wholesale cost margin of data centres across a range of scenarios, and this section compares results at the boundaries of these scenarios. **We first layer assumptions of a low data centre demand scenario, and a With Additional Measures renewables capacity pathway (the most ambitious of the three outlined above), alongside a price shock of the exact magnitude modelled in Scenario 2. For contrast, we also layer the assumptions of a high data centre demand scenario, and the least ambitious renewables capacity pathway (With Existing Measures), alongside the same price shock.** For brevity, these will be called Comparative Scenario 1 and Comparative Scenario 2, respectively.

The research motivation here is not to draw spurious contrasts between extreme scenarios. The scenarios explored in this report are based on robust inputs from official sources and represent likely and plausible development pathways for Ireland's data centre sector and future renewables capacity.

Within the range of these plausible outcomes, the interaction between policy decisions to facilitate a further surge in data centre energy consumption and to not commit to an ambitious renewables transitions can leave households further exposed to price shocks in a future of volatile energy markets, and, more generally, to the price effects of an inflexible baseload of a data centre sector consuming as much as 30% of power within the Irish state by 2030 in a gas-dependent electricity market.

6.2. Comparative scenarios results

Table 10 shows the gross wholesale costs which households may pay from 2025-2034 due to the presence of data centre demand across both comparative scenarios. Comparative Scenario 1, with lower data centre (and overall) energy demand and higher renewable energy capacity with a price shock across 2030-31, could still impose additional wholesale costs on households to the tune of **€323** across the ten year scenario period. By contrast, Comparative Scenario 2, defined by significantly higher data centre demand and lower renewables capacity could result in significantly high wholesale electricity costs for households, estimated at **€759**.

The same price shock outlined in Scenario 2 in the above sections has been applied across comparative scenarios here. Crucially, therefore, the drivers of some **€435** in additional costs for the average household between the two scenarios, are directly down to the consequences of government policy regarding data centre expansion and renewables build out to lower dependence on gas-fired power.

Table 10 – Gross data centre wholesale cost effect for Comparative Scenario 1 and 2, 2025-2034

	Comparative Scenarios - Data centre demand, renewables pathways, and price shocks										
	Cumulative Total	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031	2032	2033	2034
Comparative Scenario 1	355.1	36.1	35.5	34.7	33.8	32.8	57.0	41.3	28.7	28.0	27.2
Comparative Scenario 2	850.6	59.8	69.0	76.1	80.7	84.4	132.3	107.9	81.2	80.3	78.9
Annual difference	495.5	23.7	33.5	41.3	46.9	51.5	75.3	66.6	52.5	52.3	51.8

These are not insignificant costs. Multiplying these average household values by total projected households out to 2034, the total cumulative costs across all households in the ten years 2025-2034 could total **€696 million in Comparative Scenario 1, and €1.64 billion in Comparative Scenario 2**. The difference between these scenarios driven by government policy and a modelled price shock, therefore, could total **€941 million cumulatively from 2025-2034**.

7. Discussion and conclusions

7.1. Summary of key findings

The modelling exercise undertaken in this report offers approximated values for households costs incurred by the constant, inflexible and rising share of data centre power demand in Ireland. Whilst the cost effects are modelled based on a range of assumptions and robust inputs, the underlying trends are clear.

A rapidly expanding data centre sector, checked by a moratorium in 2021 but now set to continue, decoupled from a sufficient rise in renewable energy capacity, appears to have produced dynamics within the Irish electricity market which can increase wholesale costs for Irish households.

Based on results in this report, these estimated costs are marginal in the early years of data centre expansion. However, as the sector expands rapidly throughout the late 2010s, and coincides with extraordinary energy market volatility and a stubborn dependence on imported gas as the primary means of generating power, the consistent presence of data centre demand on the grid pushes wholesale electricity costs further up the merit order curve, where gas becomes a price setter more often. This has left Irish households exposed to significant estimated wholesale cost increases due to this interaction effect.

In 2022, a year of extraordinary energy price increases where this effect has been most significant, the data centre wholesale cost margin may have been an estimated 8.5% of total average residential bills.

Modelling a range of future scenarios highlights the centrality of this gas-dependence and data centre power consumption interaction effect. Results in Scenario 2 show the possibility of renewables mitigating the approximated data centre wholesale price effect, but in almost none of the scenarios modelled for this report is the renewables development pathway sufficient to fundamentally alter the interaction effect between constantly high data centre demand and gas dependence. In every case except the final years of our scenario period in the lowest demand and highest renewables assumptions, continued growth in data centre demand would appear to create a significant wholesale cost effect, failure to reduce dependency on gas power, and impose additional significant costs on households.

By introducing a stylised price shock in 2030 based on a stylised scenario drawn from the energy price spike of the summer of 2022, shows that in higher demand scenarios, the data centre price effect in periods of crisis, is more intense.

As noted throughout this study, these results pose significant questions for policy makers in Ireland regarding the future growth of data centre demand, suggesting a need to intervene and limit demand from data centres in order to manage use of resources and reduce additional costs on households. Additional costs for households, as outlined in the modelling, represent a significant quantity of foregone household spending that would be committed to wholesale electricity costs through electricity suppliers (assuming 100% wholesale cost pass-through), instead of to other essential household commodities.

7.2. Modelling limitations

Some limitations in the modelling approach for this report exist. For example, the conceptual underpinning of the residual demand-price curve, whilst robust in its assumptions and substantiated

by past data, is merely a proxy for merit order operations. This is due to significant data constraints – i.e. the lack of a robust, publicly available merit order data in a high resolution time series.

Furthermore, the regression model used to approximate future wholesale prices through residual demand is trained on past data which does not include solar power, due to its effective absence of the Irish energy mix from 2015-2023. In other words, it approximates a residual demand-log price relationship based on total demand, minus available wind energy, and wholesale prices. Future renewables pathways modelled in this report, however, do assume significant solar capacity. It is an acknowledged limitation that the effect of solar power on the residual demand-log price relationship is conflated with that of residual demand derived from wind availability and log wholesale prices 2015-2023. This model also produces data centre cost effect estimates in a very small number of average annual residual demand values which are negative - it is acknowledged in this report that in these select cases, the model output should not be interpreted as a data centre-gas dependence interaction effect.

The impacts of constraint and curtailment are not modelled. Whilst ENTSO-E data provides a spot price, and EirGrid offer robust high resolution data for dispatched available wind energy, on an hourly basis for the lengthy time series analysed in this study, a similarly detailed time series of curtailed wind energy is not available. In approximating the merit order curve through a residual demand-price relationship, the counterfactual of curtailed wind being more readily available to move residual demand down the cost curve is not modelled.

Though this is included as a possible limitation of this study for transparency purposes, the location of data centres themselves create constraint and curtailment, to a degree, in the Irish electricity market. Indeed, based on past research (Mamkhezri et al, 2025)⁵⁷ this may also be a factor influencing wholesale electricity prices in Ireland (a relationship not modelled here). With the majority of data centres co-locating around Dublin, it is difficult to ensure renewable power can be transmitted efficiently to the point of demand – when this occurs, dispatched energy, typically gas, is required.

Future wholesale price estimation in the three modelled scenarios from 2025-2034 is a further limitation of this study. In a period of extremely volatile energy markets, whose instability has not yielded in the wake of the US-Israeli war against Iran, it is a limited modelling input to assume log wholesale price data will follow past trends (2015-2023). Whilst this approach in a log-linear regression model accounts for exponential features of the residual demand-price curve, it is far from a perfect method to approximate future prices. In a stylised way, at least, Scenario 2 accounts for some future instability and the consequent impact on the data centre wholesale price effect analysed in this report. Future research exploring other approaches to integrate future cost approximation with data centre residual demand curve pressure would be an exciting contribution to the research questions approached in this report.

7.3. Conclusion

This report is a modelling exercise. It does not claim to predict the future, and all results in the above sections are estimates. The purpose of any modelling is to use robust data inputs alongside conceptually sound underpinnings and interactions between variables, to reveal and quantify trends and relationships. The trends and relationships made clear in this report is the interaction effect

⁵⁷ https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=5736562

between largely inhibited data centre energy consumption growth, gas-fired power dependency, and wholesale electricity prices.

A robust conclusion, therefore, is that rapid growth of data centre energy consumption in Ireland, unprecedented for any high-income, European country, appears to create significant additional costs in the Irish wholesale electricity market. The rapid growth of data centres, consuming almost all new renewables capacity in recent years, has reinforced a dependence on gas power. Additionally, the constant and rising presence of data centres on the grid creates a clear price effect through our simulated merit order curve (the residual demand-price curve). If future projections and recent policy announcements about further data centre expansion transpire in the future, then this effect will continue, and may compound.

In an era of drastic ecological overshoot and planetary crisis, despite widespread social need being unmet (including the many Irish households in energy poverty), we must prioritise the use of energy and resources to improve our wellbeing, tackle inequality and deprivation, and put the needs of citizens first.

A near future where data centres consume some 30% of all electricity in the Irish state, thereby imposing further estimated costs on households in a prolonged 'cost of living' crisis, begs important questions of policymakers about the social, economic, and ecological priorities of the current model of Irish development.

As Europe grapples with another energy crisis and simultaneously looks to speed up data centre rollout across the continent (for example the European Commission's AI Continent Plan⁵⁸ which aims to triple data centre capacity in the coming years), this analysis should serve as a cautionary example of the risks to consumers of heavy reliance on gas in the power system combined with consistently high and inflexible data centre demand.

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⁵⁸ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ai-continent-action-plan>